

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

this certificate is proudly presented to

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Raxmatullayeva Munajat Nozimjon qizi

INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA MODAL FE'LLARNING
LINGVOKOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2022-DEKABR